

TO ASSESS THE ROLE OF MANSIK BHAVAS IN THE ETIOPATHOGENESIS OF ANIDRA (INSOMNIA)'- A LITERARY REVIEW

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Article Received on 05 Nov. 2025,

Article Revised on 25 Nov. 2025,

Article Published on 01 Dec. 2025,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17934211>

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How to cite this Article: Dr. Archana Modi¹, Prof. (Dr.) Avadhesh Kumar², Dr. Prem Kant Yadav³. (2025). TO ASSESS THE ROLE OF MANSIK BHAVAS IN THE ETIOPATHOGENESIS OF ANIDRA (INSOMNIA)'- A LITERARY REVIEW. World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 14(12), 2121–2140.

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ABSTRACT

According to Ayurveda, nidra is one of the most important elements that contribute to a healthy existence. It is one of the three pillars, or trayopastambhas, that support an individual's health. Excellent scientists from every nation have attempted to investigate the nature and causes of sleep. In Ayurveda, anidra is not described as a distinct illness, and as a result, there is no Samprapti. Anidra's dushya involvement is described based on the Dosha. Sleep is the unintentional absence of knowledge or mental waves. A condition of awareness when the sense of existence is retained is called dreamless sleep. Perceptual senses rest in the mind while we sleep, and the mind rests in the awareness, which rests in the being. The intricate confluence of Atma, Sharira, and Satva is life. As a result, the mind, body, and soul are interdependent. The person sleeps after withdrawing from their objects due to exhaustion of the mind and indriyas. Impaired general mental functioning, alpa Satva,

vitiating of both sharirika (vata, pitta, and kapha) and manasa dosha (rajo and tama), as well as vitiating of manovaha srotasa, are said to be the causes of anidra. Vitiating vata causes

bhaya, shoka, moha, dinta, and other problems and hinders Manas' enjoyment. In the etiopathogenesis and aggravation of the condition, these Mansika bhavas are essential. Manas play an important role in the loss of sleep. The heart communicates with the brain and the rest of the body in following ways i.e. neurologically, biochemically, biophysically and energetically.

KEYWORDS: Ayurveda, Nidra, Anidra, Sleep, Classification of Anidra, Nidana Panchaka., Manasa, Manasa bhava, dosha.

INTRODUCTION

When Nidra is properly experienced, it is clear from reading the previous description that it is not only a significant but also necessary aspect of existence that has an equal impact on the body and the mind. If not, inappropriate Nidra (Anidra) causes a lot of issues, including klibata, abala, dukha, karshya, and agyaan which ultimately results in death.^[1] Without providing an explanation of management at Chikitsa sthana or elsewhere, Charaka^[2] describes Nidra and Nidranasha in the context of ninditiya purusha at sutra sthana, which is covered in 80 nanatmaja Vata vikaras.^[3] The chapter on garbhavyakaranashariram may be where Susruta^[4] explains how Nidra contributes to the body's development and nutrition. In the same chapter, he also describes Chikitsa (therapy) and Vaikarika Nidra (sleep disorders). While describing trayopastambha, Vruddha Vagbhata^[5] of Astanga sangraha mentions Nidra and Nidra vikara along with treatment in viruddhaannavijnaniya adhyaya. In Vagbhata^[6] of Astanga hridaya, the same is stated in annaraksha adhyaya. Anidra in Vatajananatmaj vikara, Alpa Nidra in Pittajananatmaja vikara, and Ati Nidra in Kaphajananatmaja vikara are all described in Sarangadhara.^[7] Life is the intricate combination of Sharira, Atma, and Satva. So the mind, body, and spirit all have an impact on each other.^[8] It is believed that nidra is one of life's fundamental instincts. Adequate sleep is necessary to attain sukha, pushti, bala, vrishta, gyan, and jeevan.^[9] The mind's stimulant and controller, according to Acharya Charak, is Vata Dosha.^[10] Stressors such as Shoka, Bhaya, Krodha, Chinta, and other disrupted Manasa bhava are major contributors to Anidra. Anidra belongs to the 80 different kinds of nanatmaja vatavyadhies.^[11] The symptoms of vitiation of vata include jumbha, angamarda, tandra, shirogaurava, akshigaurava, jadyata, glani, bhrama, apakti, and vata roga.^[12] Nidan is adikarana, which translates to "Mukhya karana,^[13] or the primary reason. The production of Manas vikara is considered to be by the impairment of general mental

functions, the presence of alpa Satva, vitiation of both sharirika (vata, pitta and kapha) and manasa dosha (rajo and tama) and also by vitiation of manovaha srotas.^[14]

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

1. To explore the importance of Nidra.
2. To study the causes of Anidra (Insomnia)
3. To assess the Role of Mansik Bhavas In The Etiopathogenesis of Anidra (Insomnia)

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The Brihatrayi and its commentaries, the Laghutrayi as well as other Ayurvedic and contemporary texts, various research articles provided information on Anidra (Insomnia).

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Definition of Anidra: The term "anidra" refers to any condition in which the body's tama guna and kapha are reduced. Anidra is generally defined as loss of sleep or abnormalities in the quantity and quality of sleep.^[15]

Synonyms of Anidra

- **Alpa Nidra**

Alpa means less which refers to reduction in sleep time.

- **Jagarana**

Jagarana means awaken; Nidra rahita, Nidra abhava which refers to the loss of sleep or no sleep.

- **Nidrakshaya**

Kshaya means harsa, bhanga so; Nidrakshaya term refers to disturbances in sleep reduction in sleep time.

- **Nidrabhanga**

The word bhanga means breaking, splitting; this term shows disturbances of sleep.

- **Nidrachheda**

Chheda means cutting off, a section, which shows disturbances during sleep.

- **Nidrabhramsha**

The term 'bhramsha' means to drop, fall down, cessation; which refers to reduction in sleep

time.

- **Vigata Nidra**

The term 'vigata' means disappear, ceased which can be correlated with loss of sleep or reduction in sleep time.

- **Nasta Nidra**

Nasta means lost and disappeared deprived of which convey the meaning of loss of sleep. By going through all these synonyms Nidra nasha can be considered as difficulty in initiation of sleep reduction in sleep time and disturbances during sleep.

ADVANTAGE OF NIDRA AND DISADVANTAGE OF ANIDRA - Acharya Charak discusses the significance of nidra as a Sukha (happiness), Pushti (nourishment), Bala (strength), Vrishata (aphrodisiac), Gyaan (knowledge), Jeevankar (lifegiving), whereas improper sleep results into Dukha (unhappiness), Karshayata (emaciation), Abala (weakness), Kleebata (impotent), Agyaan (impaired knowledge), even destroys the life.

निद्रायतंसुखंदुःखंपुष्टिःकाश्यं बलाबलं ॥

वृषताक्लीबताज्ञानमज्ञानंजीवितंनच ॥

(Cha. Su. -21/36)

NIDANA

- **Aaharaja nidana:** Excessive consumption of Ruksha Aahara, Ratriprabhutashana, Upavaasa Visamashana, Adhyashana, Alpashana, Viruddhashana, Atimadhyapana (Alcohol), and drug withdrawal effects (including alcohol) can raise the Anidra.^[16]
- **Viharaj Nidana:** Ati Dhumpana Sewan, Ratri Jagarana, Ati Sharirika Shrama, Ati Diwaswapna, Ativyavaya, and uncomfortable sleeping environment (Asukha Shayya) and Vegavidharana are a responsible factor for Anidra.
- **Mansika Nidana:** Chinta, Bhaya, Shoka, Krodha, Manasantapa, etc.

कायस्यशिरसश्चैवविकशच्छर्दनंभय ॥

चिन्ताक्रोधस्तथाधूमोव्यायामोरक्तमोक्षण ॥ 55॥

उपवासोऽसुखाशय्यासत्त्वौदार्यतमोजयः ॥

निद्राप्रसङ्गमहितंवारयन्तिसमुत्थित ॥ 56॥

एतएवचविज्ञेयानिद्रानाशस्यहेतवः ॥

कार्यकालोविकारश्चप्रकृतिर्वायुरेवच || 57||

(Cha. Su. 21/55-57)

- **Improper treatment:** Atiyoga of Vaman, Virechana, Dhumapana, Raktamokshana, Vyayam etc. causes the vitiation of Vata.^[17]
- (Vyadhi), individual constitution (prakruti), injuries (Abhigata), and depletion (Kshaya) also contribute to disturbed sleep.
- Understanding these factors allows Ayurveda to address insomnia holistically, focusing on restoring doshic balance for effective management. Mainly for kapha kshaya. By advancement of ageing, internal biological clock that regulates sleep, creeps slightly forward, compelling older people to go to sleep earlier and to wake earlier.

PURVARUPA: Purvarupa is not described for Anidra in any Ayurvedic classics.

ROOPA: A Cardinal feature of Anidra is loss of sleep. Another symptom is Jrumbha, Angamarda, Tandra, Shiroroga, Shirogaurav, Akshigaurav, Jadya, Glani, Bhrama, Apakti, Vata roga etc.^[18]

जृम्भाऽङ्गमर्दस्तन्द्रा च शिरोरोगोऽक्षिगौरवम् । (Cha.Su. 7/22)

निद्रानाशादङ्गमर्दशिरोरौरवजृम्भिकाः ।

जाड्यग्लानिभ्रमापक्तितन्द्रा रोगाश्च वातजाः ॥ (Ah.Su. 7/64)

SYMPTOMS OF ANIDRA

RUPA	CS	SS	AH	AS
JRUMBHA	+	+	+	+
ANGAMARDA	+	+	+	+
TANDRA	+	+	+	+
SHIRO-ROGA	+	-	-	-
SHIRO-GAURAVA	-	+	+	+
AKSHI-GAURAVA	+	+	-	-
JADYATA	-	-	+	+
GLANI	-	-	+	+
BHRAMA	-	-	+	+
APAKTI	-	-	+	+
VATAROGA	-	-	+	+

(CS- Charak samhita; SS- Susrutha samhita; AH- Ashtanga hridaya; AS- Ashtanga sangraha)

SAMPRAPTI (PATHOGENESIS) OF ANIDRA: Anidra is said to be Vata Nanatamaja Roga. If a person falls asleep while their mind, sensory organs, and motor organs are exhausted, they are dissociating themselves from their objects. Manasika dosha Raja plays a vital part in pathogenesis. The two categories of causative factors – Sharirika and Mansika—

cause vitiation of vata. Impaired psychosomatic mental processes limit Mana's capacity to dissociate from Gyanendriya and Karmendriya. This ultimately results in the pathological stage of Anidra.^[19]

Dosha: Manasa Santapa like Kama, Krodha, Shoka, Bhaya, Lobha, Moha etc. lead to Dosha Prakopa.^[20] Dosha involved in Anidra are Vata and Pitta which are in increased state while in case of Kapha, the Kshaya is usually observed. **Tarpaka kapha:** It is an auxilliary – dosha of kapha and its function is to nourish the cells of brain, restful night sleep. When this dosha is not in balance the brain cells go unnourished, causing anidra. **Prana vayu:** It is an auxilliary dosha of vata. It creates a sensitive nervous system and this together with an aggravated prana vayu cause anidra. It is also linked to depression, anxiety and Worries. **Sadhaka pitta:** It is an auxillary dosha of pitta and is found in hridaya. It controls the psychological activities and emotional stress. Any imbalance creates problems such as working too hard and too long, which ultimately leads to anidra.^[21] Chakrapani dutta described the functions of this Pitta are

Hridaya is to be known as the Sadhak agni, in as much as its function is to enable one to achieve one's aspiration.^[22]

Impairment of Basic Functions of Vata: Fundamental functions of Vata, in connection with mental operations are Activation (Pravartakaha), Controlling (Niyanta) and Motivation (Preraka). These basic functions are impaired, while Vata aggravation takes place on account of specific Nidanas. Activation function is altered due to a more heightened state of activity. This results over indulgence of Karmendriya, leading to the absence of exhausted Karmendriya state. Consequently, Mano-nivritti, a necessary requisite for Nidra, is not at all ensued. An abnormality in the controlling function leads to a very active mind. This implies that, the Rajoguna, universal motivator of everything must have been overwhelming. In addition to this, over activity of mind, causes overactivation of Gyanendriya and Karmendriya, because, Manasa is Ubhayendriya and it is juxtaposed to both. As seen earlier, this again renders a state of Mana without exhaustion. This prevents revoking of mind from its objects.^[23] Vitiating vata hampers the happiness of Manas and provokes bhaya, shoka, moha, dinta^[24] etc.

Dushya: Rasa Dhatu, has its role in the Dhatu level of Samprapti. Because it provides Tushti, Prinana – both functions are evaluated by Acharyas in the psychic level.^[25]

Agni: Here, vitiation of Jatharagni takes place, because Nidra is said to enhance the Agni.^[26]

Apakti – one symptom of Nidranasha, also indicates its vitiation. Manasika Bhavas directly lead to indigestion i.e. Agnimandya as Acharya Charaka stated that the food eaten by one who is under chinta, shoka, bhaya, krodha, dhukhashayya and ratrijagrana though, it be the prescribed diet and is eaten with strict regard to measure, will fail to be digested properly.^[27] However, in Amotpatti, also Manasika Bhavas are mentioned as a main causative factor.

Srotasa: The role of Manovaha Srotasa can be understood without any controversy. Rasavaha Srotasa, in this context, too has a pivotal role in the pathogenesis. Root of Manovaha Srotasa is Hridaya and Hridaya is substantiated to the seat of Mana. Moreover, etiological factor, responsible for Rasavaha Dushti, includes mental cause such as Chintyanam Chatichintanat.^[28]

Kha-vaigunya and Srotodushti: Manasika bhavas like Anxiety, Grief are described as the main vitiating factors for Rasavaha srotodushti.^[28] The main mode of vitiation is Atipravritti. Since, the over indulgence of Manasa is a common feature of the disease.

Adhithana and Udbhavasthana: Hridaya is the abode for these two factors. It is the platform where the whole Samprapti process is supposed to be eventualised. As seen earlier, Hridaya is the bed rock for Mana and its role in Anidra is already defined by Acharyas.^[29]

So, it can be said that some of the causative factors produce weakness of dhatus i.e. Kha-vaigunya and some produce srotodushti. Hence, all these four factors Agnimandya, i.e. Dosha Prakopa, Kha-vaigunyam and Srotodushti ultimately lead to Sthana Sanshraya in Hridaya and cause impairment of basic functions of vata and pitta leading to Anidra. It can be ascertained that, all the three psychosomatic functions of mind, when impaired, restricts the detachment of Mana from Indriyas of both kind, seeking rest in Nirindirya Pradesha (Chakrapani), results the pathological state Anidra.

TYPES OF SAMPRAPTI

Sankhya

According to Ayurveda; Anidra is of two types i.e. either due to Vata prakopa or Pitta prakopa.^[30]

Vikalpa

In Anidra, mainly in Vata Prakopa; it's Chala and Laghu Guna vitiates, which supports the mind to be active and causing Anidra. In this way; the Dosha amshamsha kalpana is essential.

Pradhanya

In Pradhanya Samprapti; the predominance of morbid humours is described in terms of the comparative degrees. As Anidra is of Vataja Nanatmaja Vyadhi, vitiation of Vata occurs and Pitta dominance is not seen. In this way; the validation of the Dosha pradhanyata is essential.

Bala

Bala of Anidra i.e. Vyadhi can be well explained by the strength of manifestation of symptoms, severity and duration etc; which will surely help as a prognostic tool.

Kala

Kala is an essential factor; while considering Nidra as well as Anidra. Charaka^[31] describes the Nishi Kala cause Nidra naturally. Sleeping in day time is contraindicated and not advised. Not sleeping in night time; indicating that Kala interferences with cause the Anidra – thus the time factor are having an influential effect on Anidra and Nidra.

Samprapti Ghataka ; Anidra – Sampraptighataka

DOSHA	Vata And Pitta (Vridhhi),Kapha (Kshaya)
DUSHYA	Rasa
SROTAS	Manovaha And Rasavaha Srotas
SROTODUSHTI PRAKARA	Atipravritti (Over Indulgence)
ADHISTHANA	Hridaya
AGNI	Jatharagni

UPADRAVA

In Ashtanga Sangraha, it is explained that aggravated Vata is due to Anidra produces Kapha kshaya. The decreased and dried Kapha sticks in Dhamanis walls and causing Srotorodha. This finally results in so much exhaustion that eyes of the patient remain wide open and causing watery secretion from eyes. This dangerous exhaustion is Sadhya up to three days after that it becomes Asadhya.^[32]

UPASHAYA AND ANUPASHAYA

Since upashaya and anupashaya are not mentioned in the texts, they are subject to evolution. Upashaya of Anidra may include things like mamsasevana, madya, ksheera and ksheeravikaras, abhyanga, utsadana, tarpana, and snehasevana, while its anupashaya may include things like rukshanna, yavanna, dhoomapana, krodha, and shoka.

SLEEP DISTURBANCE AND ITS IMPACT ON HEALTH

Sleep is one of the foundations of good health. These fundamental routines may be disregarded because many people tend to take them for granted. Sleep disorders can cause a number of ailments, including body aches, headaches, yawning, weakness, and drowsiness. cardiovascular disease, breast cancer, diabetes mellitus, and even death.

ANIDRA MANAGEMENT

There is no prescribed course of treatment for Anidra in our Ayurvedic books. It depends on the course of treatment.

As stated, anidra can be broadly classified into two categories depending on the situation.

(1). Bahya Chikitsa, (2). Abhyantara Chikitsa

We would once more separate Abhyantara Chikitsa into two categories:

(a) Aushadha Pradhana Chikitsa and, (b) Ahara Pradhana Chikitsa.

Our ancient acharyas gave special attention to Manasika upacharas like Manoanukulavatavarana and Bahya upacharas like Moordhni Taila and Abhyanga and also Padabhayanga by ksheerbala taila. along with manonukulavishayagrahana. They also clarified the distinct aharas and therapeutic procedures for Anidra patients. We can categorize all of these therapeutic approaches in various settings into four groups: Ahara upachara, Ausadha upachara, Manasika upachara, and Bahyaupachara. We can better comprehend the value of sleep by incorporating the knowledge of Ayurveda and ancient texts into our daily lives. Activities that promote holistic health, lower stress levels, and enhance sleep quality include yoga nidra, mindfulness meditation, and conscious relaxation techniques.

Ayurvedic literature does not describe the following additional measures, yet they can be recommended to Anidra's patient

- Keeping to a regular bedtime schedule.
- Avoid smoke, drink tea, coffee, or alcohol right before bed. You should also refrain from working or reading until after midnight & Before bed, all tensions in the mind must be released.
- Suggested listening to relaxing music or favorite tunes also promotes sleep.
- Advised for 5-10 minutes meditation and foot massage before going for sleep .
- Regular offering prayer before sleep.
- Activities such as washing of hand, feet and face help inducing sleep.
- Not advised of excess coitus and Day sleep should be prohibited
- Advised for proper evacuation of stool and urine
- Advised for mosquito control measures to avoid mosquito bites
- Maintaining of adequate privacy and free from disturbances

A/C to modern science

NIDRA: Quality sleep recharges and rejuvenates the mind, improving both short term and long term mental powers. When the mind and indriyas get exhausted, they withdraw themselves from their objects and the individual sleeps.^[33] It keeps everyone lively, nourishes like mother, so called as Bhutadhatri.^[34] It is observed to have different stages: Rapid Eye

Movement Sleep and Non Rapid Eye Movement Sleep. Sleep is controlled by stopping waking mechanism of the brain and starting the sleep centers of the brain.^[35] Hormonal changes also affect sleep.^[36] Hormones are linked with sleep in a number of ways.^[37]

Hormones released in the brain during sleep

Growth hormone	Essential for growth and tissue repair Produced in the pituitary gland (in the brain) Released during sleep
Antidiuretic hormone (ADH)	Prevents the production of dilute urine Produced in the pituitary gland (in the brain) Level of ADH increases during sleep
Melatonin	Signals to the body that it is time to sleep Produced in the pituitary gland (in the brain) Released with increases darkness
Oxytocin	Involved in child birth, lactation and social behaviour Produced in the hypothalamus (base of the brain) Levels peak after 5 hours of sleep Levels may influence the content of dreams
Prolactin	Involved in over 300 functions including lactation, metabolism and immune system regulation Produced in the pituitary gland (in the brain) Levels are higher during sleep than in daytime

Hormones released in the body that relate to sleep

Ghrelin	Stimulates hunger Produced mainly by the cells that line the stomach
Insulin	Controls glucose level and how the body uses carbohydrates and fats in food Produced in the pancreas
Cortisol	Involved in metabolism, immune response and stress response Produced in the adrenal glands Levels peak just before waking, making us feel hungry and alert (wake-up signal)
Aldosterone	Helps regulate the levels of sodium and potassium in the body Produced in the Adrenal cortex Levels are high during sleep, which prevents us from needing to go to the toilet
Leptin	Regulates body weight by inhibiting hunger Produced in the adipose tissue (fat cells) During sleep levels of ghrelin in the body are regulated so that we do not become hungry

INSOMNIA: Habitual sleeplessness or simply inability to sleep for a minimum period, which is necessary for a sound mental and physical health, is called Insomnia or Chronic inability to fall asleep or remain asleep for an adequate length of time is called Insomnia. It is

the difficulty in initiating or maintaining sleep, waking up too early and unable to sleep again, or waking up with a feeling of lassitude and lethargy. Insomnia becomes a serious problem when it affects daytime performance and behavior.

- **Acute Insomnia:** This type of insomnia lasts for a short time – from several nights up to three weeks – and goes away on its own without treatment.
- **Chronic Insomnia:** Insomnia that lasts more than three weeks is classified as chronic insomnia. Nearly 1 in 10 people have chronic insomnia, which often requires some form of treatment to go away.
- **Primary insomnia:** Primary insomnia means that a person is having sleep problems that are not directly associated with any other health condition or problem.
- **Secondary insomnia:** Secondary insomnia means that a person is having sleep problems because of something else, such as a health condition (like asthma, depression, arthritis, cancer, or heart burn) pain, medication they are taking or a substance they are using (like alcohol).
- **According to Modern Medical Sciences:-** Physical pain from Arthritis, Ulcers, Migraines, Angina, Breathing disorders like Asthma, and Respiratory problems such as cold and cough, irregular heart-beat or palpitation, cramps in legs, increased frequency of urination due to diabetes mellitus etc. leads to insomnia.
- Many types of drugs may lead to insomnia such as stimulants, sedative and antidepressants, drugs acting on thyroid, contraceptives etc. can cause insomnia. Alcohol consumption also causes disturbance in sleep. Both sleeping pills and alcohol lead to fragmented sleep and frequent early awakening instead of good sound sleep.^[38]

CONCEPT OF MANAS: After sannikarsha of Atma, Indriya and Artha, the main factor whose presence or absence determines the gyanotpatti is Manasa. Charaka says that Manasa is one of the nine Dravya. Ubhayatmaka and Atiindriya manasa is Achetana but Kriyavana. The functions of Manas are Indriabhighraha, Svasyanigraha, Uhya and Vichara. It has two Gunas – Anuttva and Ekatva; two doshas – Rajas and Tamas and three types – Satvika, Rajasika and Tamasika. Sixteen types of Manasa Prakriti are described on the basis of types of Manasa.^[39] It may be said that Rajasika and Tamsika prakriti persons are more prone to psychosomatic disorders due to excess of rosha ansha and moha ansha respectively. In the same way in Sharirika Prakriti Paittika and Vatika prakriti are more prone to psychosomatic disorders as their Manasa is easily affected by krodha, ksobha etc. in comparison to kaphaja prakriti whose Manasa is not affected or affected minimally or after a long duration by these

Bhava.^[40] Manas play an important role in the loss of sleep. Tamo Guna of mind helps in creating sleep. It is associated with Kapha Dosha and helps in generation of sleep. When our mind gets disturbed due to any thought, it increases Rajo Guna which closely resembles with the Vata Dosha. Hence increase in Rajo Guna ultimately increases Vata Dosha & diminishes the effect of Tamo Guna ultimately landing the person in insomnia. Weakness may also cause the loss of sleep. According to Ayurveda weakness generally occurs due to the dominated Vata Dosha. Apart from this Ruksha Guna (dry property) of Vata Dosha causes weakness in the body.^[41]

The heart communicates with the brain and the rest of the body in following ways

- Neurologically (through transmission of nerve impulse)
- Biochemically (through hormones and neurotransmitters),
- Biophysically (through pressure waves)
- Energetically (through electromagnetic field interactions)^[42]

MANASA BHAVA/VIKARA

General Etiological Factors of Manas Vikara^[43]

- Pragyaparadha, Asatmendriyarthasamyoga and Parinama.
- Sadvritta apalana.
- Vegavarodha
- Purvajanmakrita karma.
- Prakriti viparyaya

However grossly there are two types of disease Sharirika (Somatic) and Manasika (Psychic) according to the location of disease. Chakrapani further interprets and elaborates their context and strongly postulates the psychosomatic concept of Ayurveda.^[44]

- Shariranam Sharirena, Manasanam Manasena, Shariranam Manasena, Manasanam Sharirena

Acharya Charak has given brief explanation of manasa bhava which are 22 in number. Manasika bhava like bhaya, chinta, krodha^[45], Manasantaap^[46], shoka^[47], harsha^[48] cause anidra. Detailed description of Manasa Vikara^[49,50] are given below:

मनोऽर्थाव्यभिचरणेन, विज्ञानं व्यवसायेन, रजःसङ्गेन, मोहमविज्ञानेन, क्रोधमभिद्रोहेण, शोकं दैन्येन, हर्षमामोदेन, प्रीतितोषेण, भयं विषादेन, धैर्यमविषादेन, वीर्यमुत्थानेन, अवस्थानमविभ्रमेण, श्रद्धामभिप्रायेण,

मेधांग्रहणेन, सञ्ज्ञानामग्रहणेन, स्मृतिस्मरणेन, हियमपत्रपणेन, शीलमनुशीलनेन, द्वेषप्रतिषेधेन, उपधिमनुबन्धेन, धृतिमलौल्येन, वश्यतांविधेयतया || (Cha. Vi. 4/8)

Bhaya (Fear): It is a condition precipitated by dreadful act. It develops due to facing unwanted situation. Rajo dosha is mainly involved. Bhaya is a human emotion which makes person incapable of doing anything as a result of which mana of a person becomes restless. Increase in bhaya further leads to increase in vata dosha which ultimately leads to anidra. The victim of Bhaya can suffer from Diarrhoea. Acharya Charaka has mentioned Bhayaja Atisara among its 6 types. Its intensity is examined by Vishada.^[51] In fear the punishment centre of the limbic system is activated. It turns on the autonomic response of fight-or-flight response. Stimulation of a thin zone of periventricular nuclei of thalamus, located immediately adjacent to the third ventricle usually leads to fear. Tremors in the body parts, dryness of mouth sweating, giddiness, moha are the symptoms of bhaya. A sudden exposure to bhaya may lead to many physical and mental diseases.

Chinta (Worry): There is increase in sukshma guna of vata due to atiyoga of chinta which causes increase in mental vibrations. Hence mind becomes restless leading to lack of nidra. Sometimes individual suffer from an emotional disorder, which is psychologically just as disabling as the more extreme forms of fear but in which the individual really does not know, of what he is afraid, this is known as Chinta. Neurotic anxiety is perhaps the most important of all the symptoms in the sphere of emotions of psychopathology. The physiological concomitants which characterizes anxiety are increase blood pressure, tachycardia, increased respiration, tremors and sweating.

Krodha (Anger): One of the evils found within human mind. Krodha originates from the rajo guna and the main feature is to do harm to others. It vitiates vata and pitta and produces symptoms accordingly. This causes daha in whole body and stimulation of mana, further causing anidra. The degree of anger can be measured on the basis of intensity of Droha^[51] found in a person. Some people, when they are angry, have stomach trouble at the same time or grow red in the face. Their circulation is altered to such a degree that a headache ensues. This condition affects one's body organ like heart by several psychosomatic mechanisms. So that heart beat, blood circulations etc. are found to be increased due to excessive activation of sympathetic nerves. Symptoms of anger include teeth grinding, fist clenching, flushing, paling, prickly sensation, numbness, sweating, muscle tensions and temperature changes.

Here the punishment centre of the hypothalamus is stimulated from the external stimuli. As a result, there will be surge of catecholamines occur. The release of catecholamines triggers the fight-or-flight response in activating the the individual autonomic through system. Stimulation of the lateral hypothalamus, sometimes lead to overt rage and fighting.

Shoka (Grief): It is mental state precipitated by the loss of objects which are more beloved and in it rajo dosha is mainly involved. Vata dosha aggravates first then pitta dosha aggravation. The distress caused by shoka can lead to many ill effects. Continuous exposure to shoka for longer period can cause different physical diseases, emaciation and agnivikriti. The victim suffering from grief is seen with weeping, feeling of self-insult, with dry mouth and throat, anemic and flaccid body having regular and long expirations. The degree of Shoka can be measured on the basis of intensity of Dainya.^[51] The victim of Shoka can suffer from diarrhoea, diabetes mellitus, insomnia and pyrexia etc. A man of “Hina Sattva” can pass into “Murchha” or even death due to the acuteness of Shoka persisting for a long time. Manasika vikara as repressed negative thoughts and emotions vitiate tridosha as a result these doshas aggravate in their places called sanchaya after this if causative factors are not prevented these doshas start to affect brain and nervous system called prakopa. This causes improper secretion and flowing of neuro-hormone (prasara) to immune cells (sthanasamsraya) affecting to body organs (vyakta) and ultimately leading to physical diseases (bheda). That is Psychic phase – Sanchaya, Psychoneurotic phase - Prakopa and Prasara, Psychosomatic phase - Sthana Samsraya and Vyakti and Advanced organic phase – Bhedavastha. Insomnia has to do with something called the Stress Cycle. Whenever one feels threatened in any way the body has a mechanism called the fight or flight response that helps deal with the threat by increasing or decreasing the supply of various neurotransmitters which in turn produces dramatic changes in his physical and mental state especially emotional state, how he feels. Anger and fear, excitement and anxiety trigger the body’s ‘fight or flight and fright response. The adrenal glands flood the body with stress hormones, such as adrenaline and cortisol. The brain shunts blood away from the gut and towards the muscles, in preparation for physical exertion. Heart rate, blood pressure and respiration increase, the body temperature rises and the skin perspires. The mind is sharpened and focused. Constant flood of stress chemicals and associated metabolic changes can eventually cause harm to many different systems of the body causing short and long-term health problems like insomnia. Mental tension, stress and strain, emotional instabilities like fear complexes (Phobias), etc. have tremendous somatic impact in bringing down the digestive power.^[52]

DISCUSSION

Mansika bhava adversely affect not only the mind but also almost all the systems of the body, may sometimes endanger the life of the individual. The root cause of impaired atma-indriya-*artha samyoga* is the *pragyaparadha*. Due to the lack of intelligence, memory and will power, man is prone to commit intellectual errors. It will vitiate all the doshas especially vata, which in turn vitiates trigunas. Vitiating of tridoshas and trigunas causes impairment of all the mental and physical function. All these effects result in the development of diseases. Hypertension, fever, diabetes mellitus, insanity, insomnia, diarrhoea, hysteria, *apatanaka* and so many other diseases are found originated by these emotional factors. A mental tension affects both the voluntary system and the vegetative nerve system. By means of vegetative system the tension is communicated to the whole body, and so, with every emotion, the whole body is itself in a tension. The manifestations of this tension, however, are not as clear at every point and we speak of symptoms only in those points where the results are discoverable. If we examine more closely we shall find that every part of the body is involved in an emotional expression and that these physical expressions are the consequences of the actions of the mind and the body.

CONCLUSION

Mansikabhava like *atibhaya*, *atichinta*, *atikrodha*, *manastaap* etc. plays vital role in the etiopathogenesis and exacerbation of the disease. To correct the deranged psychosomatic setup these Mansika bhava acting as a stressor should be pacified through meditation, and adopting *sadvritta* in daily life. These pacified mansika bhavas, by correcting the vitiating state of vata, corrects the whole process of *Anidra* and results in proper functioning of the *Manas*. Ayurveda is essentially preventive in approach. Primary goal of treatment for this disease is associated with restoration of the underlying physiology. Quality of the mind is unbalanced by *manasik vikaras*, it has to be treated by controlling particular diet or habits, which play an important role in controlling *rajas* activity of mind and establishing a *tama* predominant state which is essential for *nidra*.

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